

NATIONAL – CULTURAL SPECIFIED PHRASEOLOGICAL ELLIPSIS

Erkaboeva Nargiza Tojievna

ESL teacher at Ajou University in Tashkent.

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It is known that one of the most common ways in literary form is the word or PU is the phenomenon of ellipsis. But it must be remembered that the phenomenon of ellipsis is the basic, main meaning of the phrase. Reduction of components in PUs ellipsis is a relatively rare phenomenon, but is sometimes used. Ellipsis was first described as a separate linguistic phenomenon by the Russian linguist O.I. Reunova called "Ellipsis as a Linguistic Phenomenon." in the monograph, the features of the manifestation of the ellipse, the moment of its speech and tried to shed light on key issues such as its place in literary interpretation.

The phenomenon of ellipsis is abundant in phraseology is a means of improving the external appearance that occurs. A certain of phrase in elliptical transposition belongs to another functional group on the basis of component disposal phraseologisms appear. For example, in the phrase "Og'zi qulog'iga yetdi" the omission of the verb component "yetdi" is of the phraseological meaning with the phraseology "og'zi qulog'ida" in the language occurs. Formed the second phraseology in terms of content from the first phraseology differs. But with the fact that they belong to different functional groups. If the verb phrase is "Og'zi qulog'iga yetdi", "og'zi qulog'ida" became adverbial phrase. Hence the phraseological ellipse occurs on the basis of grammatical changes. In Elliptical transposition the meaning is based on functional groups, close to the primary phraseology according to which, phraseologisms differing from it arise.

F. Chitra, a foreign linguist, said that are ellipsis could not occur in all PUs. This way shortens words allows you to express your thoughts clearly and concisely. Sometimes it is abbreviated PUs are stored in the language and used in the same form. For example, the English proverb "Curiosity killed the cat." The abbreviated form "care killed the cat" is such an ellipsis and it is a unit that is later solidified in language. In the expression of PUs in the text is not only new to its content words can appear and the order of the components can be changed. For example, the phrase "give and take" can be used to change two things at once, such as the introduction of a new component and a change in the composition of the components cases: **It was all take and no give**

The questions of phraseological ellipsis were studied by various linguists. A.V. Kunin argues that "a phraseological ellipsis is the omission of individual components of phraseological units when preservation of the denotative aspect of meaning by turns, that is, with the invariability of correlation with non-linguistic reality".¹

¹ Курс фразеологии современного английского языка, Кунин А.В., 1997

In the phenomenon of **ellipsis**, speech elements are skipped and thus stylistic changes occur, which are restored on the basis of contextual or semantic analysis and are implied in the text. The missing element is characterized by a quick recovery due to a speech situation or based on a certain contextual environment. Few know the full form of *the idiom dog in the hay - the dog lies in the hay*, does not eat and does not give to the cattle. Also the Russian phrase "Hunger is not aunt" is used in the form of an ellipsis. I wonder why "aunt" is used and not another relative. After all, this is only part of the phrase. Meaning: "Do not expect mercy from him, it is useless."

One would give his right arm for... - *borini bermoq*
"You're the kind of a girl any man in his right mind **would give his right** arm for," he said huskily. "I don't want any **right arms**" (J. Jones)

Before you could say Jack Robinson = *bir lahzada ,bir zumda*

"You run back to your company an' (= and) we'll get dinner done **before you could say Jack Robinson.**"

"I don't want to **say Jack Robinson.** And I am not going to be ordered out of my kitchen" (PA. Taylor) In modern English, some changes in phraseological units such as ellipsis can be made in Shakespearianisms. Some of these changes can be shown in the following examples.

Shakespearianism at one fell swoop ("Macbeth") - *bir zarb bilan*

became used in an abbreviated form at one swoop, resulting in quantitative variants. Quantitative variants are formed by truncating or adding elements.

They go quick, one after another - five of them vanished already **at one swoop** (S. O'Casey).

Shakespearianism wear one's heart upon one's sleeve for daws to peck at ("Othello") - *o'z hissiyotlarini ko'rsatish ;ochiqko'ngil* ← *in Modern English is ellipted* : wear one's heart upon one's sleeve.

Many Shakespearianisms acquire lexical variants over time: for example, applaud (or cheer) to the echo - noisy, enthusiastically applaud, give an ovation (applaud to the echo - Shakespearianism; "Macbeth"); cram (ram or thrust) smth. down smb.'s throat - to impose on smb. (his opinion, their views, etc.) (thrust smth. down smb.'s throat - Shakespearianism; "Titus Andronicus").

In Uzbek, the omission of words in a phraseme is an ellipsis, it is a common form-improving way in phrases. For example, the phrase "o'ylab, o'yiga yetolmaslik" "o'yiga yetolmaslik" is a version of "o'yiga yetolmaslik." also occurs on the basis of an ellipsis and changes shape. This phenomenon is common does not affect the phrase either semantically or grammatically: "Yusuf alamli o'ylarining tagiga yetolmasdi."² The phrase fell out of the sentence

"o'ylab" meaning is precise to understand. It even consists of a combination of phrases component can also be elliptical. For example, the author generalizes The phrase "yer yorilmadi, yerga kirib ketmadim".it was changed to "Uyatdan yerga kirib ketmaymanmi?"³

² Mamatov A. Antonimiya asosida frazeologik shakllanish masalalari. // O'zbek tili va adabiyoti. O'zFAN., T.,1998

³ Mamatov A. Antonimiya asosida frazeologik shakllanish masalalari. // O'zbek tili va adabiyoti. O'zFAN., T.,1998

In this case the phrase the first part is transformed and in which the writer to which phrasema can be understood even without the changing the meaning. The omission of language elements in this type of transformation of phrases it does not impair their meaning, but stylistic effect is achieved. Adding phrases - the components added to the text does not change the general meaning, but rather the expression is expressive and considerate, provides emotional-expressiveness: ".Agar bo'lsami, o'tirganlar Muhammadjon akaning ustamonligiga, pixini yorganligiga, mug'ombirligiga, qari tulkiligiga bir ovozdan tan bergan, so'ngra bu voqeani uzoq yillar davomida chet elning saqichidek hech kimga bermay lazzatlangan bo'lardilar".

It can be considered that the phrase " bir gapni hadeb chaynamoq " chet elning saqichidek "is expanded by using the phrase before the phrase. The extended phrase only expands the content of the phrase not only, but also enhances its expressiveness, the general meaning of the text increases, stylistic productivity increases. The structure and meaning of phrases can also be changed by adding structural analogies. For example, Chorasiz so'qir eru xotin, ayb ish qilib qo'ygan boladek "miq" etmay o'tirishar, Obida hayajonlanib titraganda, Olim uning oppoq qo'lini asta siqib qo'yar, parvo qilmang deya pichirlab, unga dalda berardi".The phrase " miq etmaslik." Expanded with a construction similar to "ayb ish qilib qo'ygan boladek". miq etmaslik and at the same time with the silence of the protagonists of the work describing how they feel guilty and the fears in the situation. In the following text "mol olasi sirtida , odam olasi ichida" the first part of the phraseological unit is ellipted: "*Buni qarang ,odanning olasi ichida bo'ladi deb shuni aytishadida , bo'lmasa Sodiqni shunaqa odam deb kim o'ylabdi!*"⁴

The writers also can achieve small units of the language with the help of ellipsis. The omission of language elements do not affect the meaning , it helps to achieve stylistic effect. For example , Temurlang boshini sarak-sarak qildi.- Chakki qilasan ,o'ynashmagil arbob bilan , degan gapni eshitganmisan?"⁵. Here the phrase "O'ynashmagin arbob bilan ,arbob urar har bob bilan " phrase is ellipted.

⁴ Mamatov A. Antonimiya asosida frazeologik shakllanish masalalari. // O'zbek tili va adabiyoti. O'zFAN., T., 1998

⁵Soliyev I.S., Abduvaliyev M.A. va boshqalar, Uch tilli inglizcha, o'zbekcha va ruscha izohli tarjima lug'ati. Andijon, 2006

References:

- 1.A.Mamatov in his book "Problems of phraseological stylistics" [99: 105–107]
- 2.A.Mamatov Antonimiya asosida frazeologik shakllanish masalalari. // O'zbek tili va adabiyoti. O'zFAN., T.,1998
3. A.A.Nosirov "Frazeologizmlarning chog'ishtirma (qiyosiy) tipologiyasi (proverbial) 2020
4. . Nosirov A.A. ;" Features of proverbial phraseological units ".Middle European Scientific Bulletin,volume 10 March 20215.Soliyev I.S., Abduvaliyev M.A. va boshqalar, Uch tilli inglizcha, o'zbekcha va ruscha izohli tarjima lug'ati. Andijon, 2006
6. Teliya Veronika. Phraseology as a Language of Culture. Its Role in the Representation of a Cultural Mentality. In: Cowie, Anthony Paul (ed.): Phraseology. Theory, Analysis and Applications. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1998. – P. 55–75
- 7.W. Shakespeare, RomeoandJuliet, Act I, Sc. 1
8. Курс фразеологии современного английского языка, Кунин А.В., 1997